

DIVISIBILITY PROPERTIES OF THE 5-REGULAR AND 13-REGULAR PARTITION FUNCTIONS

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Abstract

The function $b_k(n)$ is defined as the number of partitions of n that contain no summand divisible by k . In this paper we study the 2-divisibility of $b_5(n)$ and the 2- and 3-divisibility of $b_{13}(n)$. In particular, we give exact criteria for the parity of $b_5(2n)$ and $b_{13}(2n)$.

1. Introduction

A *partition* of a positive integer n is a non-increasing sequence of positive integers whose sum is n . In other words,

$$n = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \cdots + \lambda_t$$

with $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \cdots \geq \lambda_t \geq 1$. For instance, the partitions of 4 are

4, 3 + 1, 2 + 2, 2 + 1 + 1, and 1 + 1 + 1 + 1.

We denote the number of partitions of n by $p(n)$. So, as shown above, $p(4) = 5$. Note that $p(n) = 0$ if n is not a nonnegative integer, and we adopt the convention that $p(0) = 1$. The generating function for the partition function is then given by the infinite product

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(n)q^n = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - q^n)} = 1 + q + 2q^2 + 3q^3 + 5q^4 + 7q^5 + \dots .$$

Let k be a positive integer. We say that a partition is k -regular if none of its summands is divisible by k , and denote the number of k -regular partitions of n by $b_k(n)$. For example, $b_3(4) = 4$ because the partition $3 + 1$ has a summand divisible by 3 and therefore is not 3-regular. Adopting the convention that $b_k(0) = 1$, the generating function for the k -regular partition function is then

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_k(n)q^n = \prod_{\substack{n=1 \\ k \nmid n}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - q^n)} = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - q^{kn})}{(1 - q^n)}. \tag{1}$$

Note that $b_2(n)$ equals the number of partitions of n into odd parts, which Euler proved is equal to the number of partitions of n into distinct parts.

The partition function satisfies the famous Ramanujan congruences

$$\begin{aligned} p(5n + 4) &\equiv 0 \pmod{5}, \\ p(7n + 5) &\equiv 0 \pmod{7}, \\ p(11n + 6) &\equiv 0 \pmod{11} \end{aligned}$$

for every $n \geq 0$. Ono [7] proved that such congruences for $p(n)$ exist modulo every prime ≥ 5 , and Ahlgren [1] extended this to include every modulus coprime to 6. Given these facts, for a positive integer m it is natural to wonder for which values of n we have that $p(n)$ is divisible by m , or simply how often $p(n)$ is divisible by m . By the results cited above,

$$\liminf_{X \rightarrow \infty} \#\{1 \leq n \leq X \mid p(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{m}\} / X > 0$$

for any m coprime to 6. The $m = 2$ and $m = 3$ cases, meanwhile, have proven elusive.

The state of knowledge for k -regular partition functions is better. For example, Gordon and Ono [4] have shown that if p is prime, $p^v \parallel k$ and $p^v \geq \sqrt{k}$, then for any $j \geq 1$ the arithmetic density of positive integers n such that $b_k(n)$ is divisible by p^j is one. In certain cases one can find even more specific information. As an illustration we consider the parity of $b_2(n)$. Noting that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_2(n)q^n = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - q^{2n})}{(1 - q^n)} \equiv \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - q^n)^2}{(1 - q^n)} \equiv \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n) \pmod{2}$$

by Euler’s Pentagonal Number Theorem it follows that

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_2(n)q^n \equiv \sum_{\ell=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{\ell(3\ell+1)/2} \pmod{2},$$

and so $b_2(n)$ is odd if and only if $n = \ell(3\ell + 1)/2$ for some $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}$. Thus, in contrast to the case of $p(n)$ we have a complete answer for the 2-divisibility of $b_2(n)$ (see [6] and [3] for analogous results for the k -divisibility of $b_k(n)$ for $k \in \{3, 5, 7, 11\}$).

Now consider the m -divisibility of $b_k(n)$ when $(m, k) = 1$. In [2] Ahlgren and Lovejoy prove that if $p \geq 5$ is prime, then for any $j \geq 1$ the arithmetic density of positive integers n such that $b_2(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^j}$ is at least $\frac{p+1}{2p}$ (they also prove that $b_2(n)$ satisfies Ramanujan-type congruences modulo p^j). In [9] Penniston extended this to show that for distinct primes k and p with $3 \leq k \leq 23$ and $p \geq 5$, the arithmetic density of positive integers n for which $b_k(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{p^j}$ is at least $\frac{p+1}{2p}$ if $p \nmid k - 1$, and at least $\frac{p-1}{p}$ if $p \mid k - 1$ (in [11] and [12] Treneer has shown that divisibility and congruence results such as these hold for general k). The latter result indicates that a special role may be played by the prime divisors of $k - 1$, and we consider this here. Upon numerically investigating the m -divisibility of $b_k(n)$ for small values of k and m not covered by the results above, the most striking and regular patterns we found occurred for $k = 5, m = 2$ and for $k = 13$ and $m \in \{2, 3\}$.

Theorem 1. *Let n be a nonnegative integer. Then $b_5(2n)$ is odd if and only if $n = \ell(3\ell + 1)$ for some $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}$. That is,*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_5(2n)q^{2n} \equiv \sum_{\ell=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{2\ell(3\ell+1)} \pmod{2}.$$

Remark. By Euler’s Pentagonal Number Theorem, Theorem 1 is equivalent to

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_5(2n)q^{2n} \equiv \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)^4 \pmod{2}. \tag{2}$$

Theorem 2. *Let n be a nonnegative integer. Then $b_{13}(2n)$ is odd if and only if $n = \ell(\ell + 1)$ or $n = 13\ell(\ell + 1) + 3$ for some nonnegative integer ℓ . That is,*

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13}(2n)q^{2n} \equiv \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} q^{2\ell(\ell+1)} + \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} q^{26\ell(\ell+1)+6} \pmod{2}.$$

Remark. Jacobi’s triple product formula yields

$$\prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)^3 = \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} (-1)^\ell (2\ell + 1) q^{\ell(\ell+1)/2},$$

and hence Theorem 2 is equivalent to

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13}(2n)q^{2n} \equiv \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{4n})^3 + q^6 \cdot \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{52n})^3 \pmod{2}. \tag{3}$$

Theorems 1 and 2 yield infinitely many Ramanujan-type congruences modulo 2 for $b_5(n)$ and $b_{13}(n)$ in even arithmetic progressions. It turns out that our proof of Theorem 1 yields two congruences for $b_5(n)$ in odd arithmetic progressions.

Theorem 3. *For every $n \geq 0$,*

$$b_5(20n + 5) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$$

and

$$b_5(20n + 13) \equiv 0 \pmod{2}.$$

Finally, we make the following conjecture regarding the 3-divisibility of $b_{13}(n)$.

Conjecture 1. *For any $\ell \geq 2$,*

$$b_{13}\left(3^\ell n + \frac{5 \cdot 3^{\ell-1} - 1}{2}\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$$

for every $n \geq 0$.

It turns out (see Proposition 2 below) that one can reduce the verification of each of the congruences in Conjecture 1 to a finite computation. We have verified the conjecture for each $2 \leq \ell \leq 6$ (one can easily check that the conjecture does not hold for $\ell = 1$).

2. Modular Forms

We begin with some background on the theory of modular forms. Given a positive integer N , let

$$\Gamma_0(N) := \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in SL_2(\mathbb{Z}) \mid c \equiv 0 \pmod{N} \right\}.$$

Let $\mathbb{H} := \{z \in \mathbb{C} \mid \Im(z) > 0\}$ be the complex upper half plane, and for $\gamma = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in SL_2(\mathbb{Z})$ and $z \in \mathbb{H}$ define $\gamma z := \frac{az+b}{cz+d}$. Throughout, we let $q := e^{2\pi iz}$.

Suppose k is a positive integer, $f : \mathbb{H} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ is holomorphic and χ is a Dirichlet character modulo N . Then f is said to be a *modular form* of weight k on $\Gamma_0(N)$ with character χ if

$$f(\gamma z) = \chi(d)(cz + d)^k f(z) \tag{4}$$

for all $\gamma = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix} \in \Gamma_0(N)$ and f is holomorphic at the cusps of $\Gamma_0(N)$. The modular forms of weight k on $\Gamma_0(N)$ with character χ form a finite-dimensional complex vector space which we denote by $M_k(\Gamma_0(N), \chi)$ (we will omit χ from our notation when it is the trivial character). For instance, if we denote by $\theta(z)$ the classical theta function

$$\theta(z) := \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} q^{n^2} = 1 + 2q + 2q^4 + 2q^9 + \dots,$$

then $\theta^4(z) \in M_2(\Gamma_0(4))$ (see, for example, [5]).

A theorem of Sturm [10] provides a method to test whether two modular forms are congruent modulo a prime. If $f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a(n)q^n$ has integer coefficients and m is a positive integer, let $\text{ord}_m(f(z))$ be the smallest n for which $a(n) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{m}$ (if there is no such n , we define $\text{ord}_m(f(z)) := \infty$).

Theorem 4. (Sturm) *Suppose p is prime and $f(z), g(z) \in M_k(\Gamma_0(N), \chi) \cap \mathbb{Z}[[q]]$. If*

$$\text{ord}_p(f(z) - g(z)) > \frac{k}{12}[SL_2(\mathbb{Z}) : \Gamma_0(N)],$$

then $f(z) \equiv g(z) \pmod{p}$, i.e., $\text{ord}_p(f(z) - g(z)) = \infty$.

We note here that $[SL_2(\mathbb{Z}) : \Gamma_0(N)] = N \cdot \prod \left(\frac{\ell+1}{\ell}\right)$, where the product is over the prime divisors of N .

Hecke operators play a crucial role in the proofs of our results. If $f(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a(n)q^n \in \mathbb{Z}[[q]]$ and p is prime, then the action of the Hecke operator $T_{p,k,\chi}$ on $f(z)$ is defined by

$$(f | T_{p,k,\chi})(z) := \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (a(pn) + \chi(p)p^{k-1}a(n/p))q^n$$

(we follow the convention that $a(x) = 0$ if $x \notin \mathbb{Z}$). Notice that if $k > 1$, then

$$(f | T_{p,k,\chi})(z) \equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} a(pn)q^n \pmod{p}. \tag{5}$$

Moreover, if $f(z) \in M_k(\Gamma_0(N), \chi)$, then $(f | T_{p,k,\chi})(z) \in M_k(\Gamma_0(N), \chi)$. When k and χ are clear from context, we will write $T_p := T_{p,k,\chi}$.

The next proposition follows directly from (5) and the definition of $T_{p,k,\chi}$.

Proposition 1. *Suppose p is prime, $g(z) \in \mathbb{Z}[[q]]$, $h(z) \in \mathbb{Z}[[q^p]]$ and $k > 1$. Then $(gh | T_{p,k,\chi})(z) \equiv (g | T_{p,k,\chi})(z) \cdot h(z/p) \pmod{p}$.*

We will construct modular forms using Dedekind's eta function, which is defined by

$$\eta(z) := q^{\frac{1}{24}} \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)$$

for $z \in \mathbb{H}$. A function of the form

$$f(z) = \prod_{\delta|N} \eta^{r_\delta}(\delta z), \tag{6}$$

where $r_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}$ and the product is over the positive divisors of N , is called an *eta-quotient*.

From ([8], p. 18), if $f(z)$ is the eta-quotient (6), $k := \frac{1}{2} \sum_{\delta|N} r_\delta \in \mathbb{Z}$,

$$\sum_{\delta|N} \delta r_\delta \equiv 0 \pmod{24}$$

and

$$N \sum_{\delta|N} \frac{r_\delta}{\delta} \equiv 0 \pmod{24},$$

then $f(z)$ satisfies the transformation property (4) for all $\gamma \in \Gamma_0(N)$. Here χ is given by $\chi(d) := \left(\frac{(-1)^k s}{d}\right)$, where $s := \prod_{\delta|N} \delta^{r_\delta}$. Assuming that f satisfies these conditions, then since $\eta(z)$ is analytic and does not vanish on \mathbb{H} , we have that $f(z) \in M_k(\Gamma_0(N), \chi)$ if $f(z)$ is holomorphic at the cusps of $\Gamma_0(N)$. By ([8], Theorem 1.65) we have that if c and d are positive integers with $(c, d) = 1$ and $d | N$, then the order of vanishing of $f(z)$ at the cusp $\frac{c}{d}$ is

$$\frac{N}{24d(d, \frac{N}{d})} \cdot \sum_{\delta|N} \frac{(d, \delta)^2 r_\delta}{\delta}.$$

3. Proof of the Main Results

Proof of Theorem 1. We begin with the modular forms

$$f(z) := \frac{\eta^5(5z)}{\eta(z)} = q + q^2 + 2q^3 + 3q^4 + 5q^5 + \dots$$

and

$$g(z) := \eta^4(z)\eta^4(5z) = q \cdot \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)^4 (1 - q^{5n})^4. \tag{7}$$

Define the character χ_m by $\chi_m(d) := \left(\frac{m}{d}\right)$. Using the results on eta-quotients cited above we find that $f(z) \in M_2(\Gamma_0(5), \chi_5)$ and $g(z) \in M_4(\Gamma_0(5))$. Next, recall that

$$\theta^4(z) = 1 + 8q + 24q^2 + 32q^3 + \dots \in M_2(\Gamma_0(4)).$$

Notice that $(\theta^4(z))^2 \in M_4(\Gamma_0(20))$.

From (1) we have

$$\begin{aligned} f(z) &= \frac{\eta(5z)}{\eta(z)} \cdot \eta^4(5z) \\ &= \frac{q^{5/24} \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{5n})}{q^{1/24} \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)} \cdot q^{20/24} \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{5j})^4 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

$$\equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_5(n) q^{n+1} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{20j}) \pmod{2}. \tag{9}$$

It follows from Proposition 1 that

$$(f | T_2)(z) \equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_5(2n + 1)q^{n+1} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{10j}) \pmod{2}, \tag{10}$$

and hence

$$h(z) := f(z) - (f | T_2)(2z) \equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_5(2n)q^{2n+1} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{20j}) \pmod{2}. \tag{11}$$

Note that $f(z)$ and $(f | T_2)(2z)$ are in $M_2(\Gamma_0(10), \chi_5)$, and hence $h(z)$ lies in this space as well. It follows that $h^2(z)\theta^8(z) \in M_8(\Gamma_0(20))$. Now, $g^2(z) \in M_8(\Gamma_0(20))$, and one can check that the forms $h^2(z)\theta^8(z)$ and $g^2(z)$ are congruent modulo 2 out to their q^{24} terms. By Sturm's theorem we conclude that these forms are congruent modulo 2. Since $\theta(z) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, we have that $h^2(z) \equiv g^2(z) \pmod{2}$, and hence $h(z) \equiv g(z) \pmod{2}$. Then by (11) and (7),

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_5(2n)q^{2n} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{20j}) \equiv \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)^4 (1 - q^{5n})^4 \pmod{2}. \tag{12}$$

Since $(1 - q^{5n})^4 \equiv 1 - q^{20n} \pmod{2}$, (2) now follows from (12). □

Proof of Theorem 2. To begin, we define

$$u(z) := \frac{\eta^{13}(13z)}{\eta(z)} \in M_6(\Gamma_0(13), \chi_{13}).$$

We will also use the following two forms in $M_{12}(\Gamma_0(13))$:

$$v(z) := \eta^{12}(z)\eta^{12}(13z) = q^7 \cdot \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)^{12} (1 - q^{13n})^{12} \tag{13}$$

and

$$w(z) := \eta^{24}(13z) = q^{13} \cdot \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{13n})^{24}. \tag{14}$$

From (1) we have that

$$u(z) \equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13}(n)q^{n+7} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{52j})^3 \pmod{2}.$$

Then

$$(u | T_2)(z) \equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13}(2n + 1)q^{n+4} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{26j})^3 \pmod{2},$$

and hence

$$m(z) := u(z) - (u | T_2)(2z) \equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13}(2n)q^{2n+7} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{52j})^3 \pmod{2}. \tag{15}$$

Note that since $u(z)$ and $(u | T_2)(2z)$ lie in $M_6(\Gamma_0(26), \chi_{13})$, so does $m(z)$. Then since $\theta^{24}(z) \in M_{12}(\Gamma_0(52))$, we have that $m^2(z)\theta^{24}(z) \in M_{24}(\Gamma_0(52))$. Note that $v^2(z), w^2(z) \in M_{24}(\Gamma_0(52))$ as well, and one can check that the forms $m^2(z)\theta^{24}(z)$ and $v^2(z) + w^2(z)$ are congruent modulo 2 out to their q^{168} terms. By Sturm's theorem we conclude that

$$m^2(z)\theta^{24}(z) \equiv v^2(z) + w^2(z) \pmod{2},$$

and therefore $m(z)\theta^{12}(z) \equiv v(z) + w(z) \pmod{2}$. Since $\theta(z) \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$, we find that $m(z) \equiv v(z) + w(z) \pmod{2}$. Then (15), (13) and (14) give

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13}(2n)q^{2n+7} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{13j})^{12} &\equiv q^7 \cdot \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)^{12} (1 - q^{13n})^{12} \\ &\quad + q^{13} \cdot \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{13n})^{24} \pmod{2}, \end{aligned}$$

which implies (3). □

Proof of Theorem 3. We prove only the first congruence, as the second can be proved in a similar way. Sturm's theorem gives that $f(z)$ and $(f | T_2)(z)$ are congruent modulo 2, which by (10) yields

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_5(2n + 1)q^{n+1} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{10j}) \equiv q \cdot \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - q^{5n})^5}{(1 - q^n)} \pmod{2}.$$

Then

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_5(2n + 1)q^{n+1} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{10j}) \equiv q \cdot \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1 - q^{5n})}{(1 - q^n)} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{5j})^4 \pmod{2},$$

and hence

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_5(2n + 1)q^n \equiv \sum_{\ell=0}^{\infty} b_5(\ell)q^\ell \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{10j}) \pmod{2}. \tag{16}$$

Note that $2n + 1$ has the form $20m + 5$ if and only if $n \equiv 2 \pmod{10}$. Since the infinite product on the right hand side of (16) only produces powers of q that are 0 modulo 10, it suffices to show that

$$b_5(10n + 2) \equiv 0 \pmod{2} \tag{17}$$

for all $n \geq 0$. One can easily check that the congruence $6\ell^2 + 2\ell \equiv 2 \pmod{10}$ has no solution, and so (17) follows from Theorem 1. □

With regard to Conjecture 1, we have the following elementary proposition.

Proposition 2. *Let $\ell \geq 2$. If the congruence*

$$b_{13} \left(3^\ell n + \frac{5 \cdot 3^{\ell-1} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$$

holds for all $0 \leq n \leq 7 \cdot 3^{\ell-1} - 3$, then it holds for all $n \geq 0$.

Proof. The idea of our proof is to repeatedly apply the T_3 operator to the modular form

$$P_\ell(z) := \frac{\eta(13z)}{\eta(z)} \cdot \eta^e(13z),$$

where $e := 4 \cdot 3^\ell$. By the criteria for eta-quotients cited above, $P_\ell(z) \in M_{\frac{e}{2}}(\Gamma_0(13), \chi_{13})$.

For each $1 \leq t \leq \ell$ let

$$\delta_t := \frac{13 \cdot 3^{t-1} + 1}{2}.$$

Then

$$P_\ell(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13}(n) q^{n+\delta_\ell} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{13j})^e.$$

Note that

$$P_\ell(z) \equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13}(n) q^{n+\delta_\ell} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{3^\ell \cdot 13j})^4 \pmod{3}.$$

Using Proposition 1 and the fact that $\delta_t \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$ for $2 \leq t \leq \ell$, an easy induction argument gives that $(P_\ell | T_3^s)(z)$ is congruent modulo 3 to

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13} \left(3^s n + \left(\frac{3^s - 1}{2} \right) \right) q^{n+\delta_{\ell-s}} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{3^{\ell-s} \cdot 13j})^4$$

for any $1 \leq s \leq \ell - 1$. In particular,

$$(P_\ell | T_3^{\ell-1})(z) \equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13} \left(3^{\ell-1} n + \left(\frac{3^{\ell-1} - 1}{2} \right) \right) q^{n+7} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{39j})^4 \pmod{3}.$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} (P_\ell | T_3^\ell)(z) &\equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13} \left(3^{\ell-1} (3n + 2) + \left(\frac{3^{\ell-1} - 1}{2} \right) \right) q^{\frac{(3n+2)+7}{3}} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{13j})^4 \\ &\equiv \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} b_{13} \left(3^\ell n + \frac{5 \cdot 3^{\ell-1} - 1}{2} \right) q^{n+3} \cdot \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^{13j})^4 \pmod{3}. \end{aligned}$$

Since $(P_\ell | T_3^\ell)(z) \in M_{\frac{e}{2}}(\Gamma_0(13), \chi_{13})$, by Sturm's theorem we have that if $\text{ord}_3((P_\ell | T_3^\ell)(z)) > 7 \cdot 3^{\ell-1}$, then $(P_\ell | T_3^\ell)(z) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. Therefore, if the congruence

$$b_{13} \left(3^\ell n + \frac{5 \cdot 3^{\ell-1} - 1}{2} \right) \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$$

holds for all $0 \leq n \leq 7 \cdot 3^{\ell-1} - 3$, then it holds for all $n \geq 0$. □

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